

Synthesis and characterization of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} coordination polymers derived from 1,4-benzene- and 1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate and 2-aminobenzothiazole

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Abstract : A series of coordination polymers of the general formula [M(CAR)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_xH₂O (M = Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}; CAR = BDC (1,4-benzenedicarboxylate) or FDC (1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate); ABZ = 2-aminobenzothiazole and x = 0 or 2) has been prepared and characterized. The structure of the complexes has been assigned based on elemental analysis, IR and electronic spectral, thermal analysis, scanning electron microscope and cyclic voltammetric studies. Thermogravimetry (TG), differential thermogravimetry (DTG) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) have been used to study the thermal decomposition of the complexes. The kinetic parameters have been calculated making use of the Coats-Redfern and Horowitz-Metzger equations. The antimicrobial activity of the compounds was also tested.

Keywords : Coordination polymers, spectral studies, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

1,4-Benzenedicarboxylate and 1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate and their metal complexes are of considerable interest due to their chemical and biological importance^{1,2}. Aromatic polycarboxylates, such as BDC and FDC have been well used to construct coordination frameworks³ by direct interaction with metal ions to form discrete polynuclear⁴, 1-, 2- and 3-D coordination networks⁵. 1,4-Benzenedicarboxylate is involved in a variety of bridging modes and possesses a strong tendency to form large, tightly bound metal cluster aggregates and it has been used as a building block to construct some porous coordination frameworks⁶. A number of publications was dealing with the investigation of coordination polymers comprising BDC or FDC and nitrogen donors⁷⁻¹¹. Thiazoles are not yet involved in any coordination polymers of BDC or FDC. Furthermore, thiazoles represent a very interesting class of compounds due to their pharmaceutical, analytical and industrial applications¹². Due to the above importance of both the dicarboxylates and thiazoles, it was worthwhile to synthesize and characterize a number of copper(II), cadmium(II) and lead(II) coordination polymers containing 1,4-benzenedicarboxylate, 1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate and 2-aminobenzothiazole ligands.

Fig. 1. Structures of the ligands.

Results and discussion

The complexes were prepared by the reaction of 1,4-benzenedicarboxylate or 1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate with the metal salts and 2-aminobenzothiazole (ABZ) (eqs. 1-3). The prepared complexes were found to react in the molar ratio 1 : 1 : 1 metal : BDC or FDC : ABZ. The complexes are air stable, insoluble in common organic solvents but partially soluble in DMF and DMSO. The conductivity of the complexes were measured in DMSO using 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes. The molar conductivity values of the complexes indicate their non-electrolyte nature. The compositions of the complexes are supported by the elemental analysis are recorded together with color and molar conductance values in Table 1.

IR spectra :

The most relevant infrared spectral bands of the ternary complexes are given in Table 2. The IR spectra of

cm^{-1} , has shifted to a lower wave number appearing in the range $3150\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes and suggesting coordination of the amino nitrogen to the metal(II) ions¹⁶. Metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bonding are manifested by the existence of bands in the $505\text{--}514\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 410 cm^{-1} regions, respectively¹⁷.

Electronic spectra :

The UV-Vis spectra of the complexes have been recorded in DMSO. The spectra display two distinct bands in the ranges $35460\text{--}37735$ and $27114\text{--}33333\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions within the carboxylate and ABZ ligands^{18,16}. The Cu^{II} complex **1** exhibits a band at 21331 cm^{-1} corresponding to a $d\text{--}d$ transition.

Table 1. Colors, elemental analysis, melting points and conductance data of the compounds

Complex	Color	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				M.p./Dec. (°C)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		C	H	N	S		
[Cu(FDC)(ABZ)(H ₂ O)] _n · 2H ₂ O 1	Dark-brown	41.08 (42.27)	2.96 (3.73)	5.42 (5.18)	5.74 (5.94)	220	5.22
[Cd(BDC)(ABZ)(H ₂ O)] _n 2	Light-yellow	41.31 (40.51)	2.89 (2.72)	5.72 (6.29)	6.91 (7.21)	256	6.90
[Pb(BDC)(ABZ)(H ₂ O)] _n 3	White	33.72 (33.39)	1.96 (2.23)	4.75 (5.19)	5.45 (5.94)	210	4.28

Table 2. Infrared spectral data of the coordination polymers

Compd.	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ asym.	$\nu(\text{COO})$ asym.	$\nu\Delta$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$
1	3190	1540	1360	180	1638	740	3400	410	514
2	3170	1568	1384	184	1640	740	3360	410	505
3	3160	1566	1386	180	1636	740	3400	410	510

the prepared compounds show two bands in the ranges $1540\text{--}1568$ and $1360\text{--}1386\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylic groups of the BDC or FDC coordinated to metal center. Furthermore, the IR spectra of the complexes showed a separation value $\Delta\nu \leq 184\text{ cm}^{-1}$ pointing to a bidentate mode of coordination for the carboxylate group^{13,14}. It is found that the CSC band of the azole at $\sim 740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is almost unchanged in the respective complexes, indicating that the thiazole-S is not involved in the bonding¹⁵. The same is true for the $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibration of the azole for all complexes where no appreciable shift was noticed. However, the stretching vibration of the amino group in the free ABZ observed at 3220

Thermal studies :

The thermal decomposition of the compounds **2** and **3** has been investigated in dynamic air from ambient temperature to $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As a representative example the thermogram of the lead complex **3** is depicted in Fig. 4. It shows four decomposition steps occurring in the temperature ranges $117\text{--}149$, $150\text{--}213$, $214\text{--}430$ and $432\text{--}751\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In the first step the coordinated water molecule is released (calcd. 3.33% , found 2.92%). The corresponding DTG peak occurs at $134\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and an endothermic peak appears at $138\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the DTA trace. The second and third steps indicate the decomposition of the ABZ molecule (calcd. 27.84% , found 25.23%), with a corresponding two DTG peaks at 198 and $499\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and two exother-

Fig. 2. Suggested structure of the complexes.
[M(BDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n; M = Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}

Fig. 3. Suggested structure of [Cu(FDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n.2H₂O.

Fig. 4. TG, DTG and DTA thermograms of [Pb(BDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n in dynamic air.

mic peaks at 201 and 498 °C in the DTA trace, respectively. The fourth step is commensurate with the decomposition of the BDC moiety (calcd. 30.42%, found 28.26%) with a DTG peak at 501 °C and an exothermic broad peak in the DTA trace at 503 °C. The final product is assigned to the oxide PbO (calcd. 41.7%, found 42.00%).

Kinetic analysis :

Non-isothermal kinetic analysis of the complexes was carried out applying two different procedures : the Coats-Redfern¹⁹ and the Horowitz-Metzger²⁰ methods. The correlation coefficient *r* is computed using the least squares

Table 3. Thermal decomposition data of the compounds in dynamic air

Compd.	Step	TG/DTG			Mass loss (%)
		T _i	T _m	T _f	
2	1st	75	170	202	3.38
	2nd	203	315	401	32.22
	3rd	403	462	751	35.99
3	1st	117	134	149	2.92
	2nd	150	198	213	15.59
	3rd	214	382	470	6.64
	4th	472	501	751	28.26

T_i = Initial temperature, T_m = maximum temperature and T_f = final temperature.

method. Linear curves were drawn for different values of *n* ranging from 0 to 2. The value of *n*, which gave the best fit, was chosen as the order parameter for the decomposition stage of interest. The kinetic parameters were calculated according to the above two methods for the first step of compounds 2 and 3 (Table 4).

Table 4. Kinetic parameters of the thermal decomposition of the compounds

Compd.	Step	Coats-Redfern equation			Horowitz-Metzger equation		
		<i>r</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>E</i>
2	1st	1	1.00	53.7	1	1.00	54.4
3	1st	1	1.00	57.0	0.9997	0.50	52.59

E in kJ mol⁻¹.

X-Ray powder diffraction :

The cadmium complex 2 was chosen for X-ray powder diffraction studies. The crystal lattice parameter were computed with the aid of the computer program TREOR. The crystal data of the Cd^{II} mixed-ligand complex belong to the crystal system triclinic. The crystal data are recorded in Table 5.

Table 5. The crystal data of the complex 2

Compd.	<i>a</i> (Å)	<i>b</i> (Å)	<i>c</i> (Å)	α	β	γ	Volume of unit cell (Å ³)	Crystal system
2	9.48	9.36	15.84	118.8	46.85	91.65	793.10	Triclinic

Voltammetric studies :

The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of the three studied complexes were investigated between +0.1 → -1.0 V. From careful inspection of the literature, the three

ligands under investigation are not reduced using mercury electrode, whereas 1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate is oxidized at solid electrodes^{21,22}. As a representative example the cyclic voltammetric behaviour of the Cu^{II} complex **1** was studied in DMSO and in the presence of 0.1 M tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP). Fig. 5 shows the cyclic voltammograms of 1×10^{-4} M complex recorded in the potential range +0.1 → -1.0 V and 100

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammograms of 1×10^{-4} M of [Cu(FDC)-(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n·2H₂O in presence of 0.1 M TBAP at a mercury electrode, scan rate = 100 mV/s.

mV s⁻¹ scan rate. The copper complex exhibits well defined redox system Cu^{II}/Cu⁰ with E_p values at -0.13 and -0.07 V for cathodic and anodic peaks, respectively. It was observed that the difference between the cathodic and anodic peak potentials (ΔE_p) is of the order 60 mV. It is actually twice the peak to peak separations in comparison to Nernstian value (30 mV) observed for a reversible two-electron transfer process.

As a general conclusion for the voltammetric behaviour of the three complexes, it is found that at hanging mercury drop electrode they show a single cathodic or anodic peak for each one. The appearance of the anodic peak for the three complexes indicates that the reduction is not totally irreversible. Therefore it is concluded that the central metal ion is reduced in a 2-electron quasi-reversible process.

Microbiological screening :

The complexes were tested for their biological activity against six fungal and five bacterial species (Table 6).

Table 6. Microbiological screening of the complexes

Compd.	<i>B. cereus</i> (Gram +ve)	<i>S. aureus</i> (Gram +ve)	<i>S. marcescens</i> (Gram -ve)	<i>E. coli</i> (Gram -ve)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (Gram -ve)	<i>T. rubrum</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	<i>G. candidum</i>	<i>S. brevicautis</i>
1	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	20	8	20	10	12	22	20	22	12	10	18
3	0	10	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) :

The scanning electron micrographs of the complexes 1 and 2 are given in Figs. 6 and 7. The compounds are crystalline and the size of the particles is indicated under each figure in μm .

Fig. 6. SEM of [Cu(FDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)].2H₂O.

Fig. 7. SEM of [Cd(BDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)].

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All chemical were of analytical grades. 1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid and 2-aminobenzothiazole were E. Merck grade. 1,1'-Ferrocenedicarboxylic acid was a Fluka grade. They were purchased and used without purification.

Preparation of the complexes :

Preparation of [Cu(FDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n.2H₂O :

To an ethanolic solution (15 ml) of CuCl₂.2H₂O (0.186 g, 1.1 mmol) an aqueous solution of 1,1'-ferrocenedicarboxylate (0.3 g, 1.1 mmol in 15 ml 0.1 M NaOH) was added dropwise and with stirring, then an

ethanolic solution (10 ml) of ABZ (0.164 g, 1.1 mmol) was allowed to mix with the solution mixture with continuous stirring for about 2 h. The mixture was left overnight and the precipitated dark brown copper(II) complex was filtered, washed with distilled water and ethanol and then dried over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Preparation of [Cd(BDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n and [Pb(BDC)(ABZ)(H₂O)]_n :

Preparation of the above coordination polymers followed essentially the same procedure. They were prepared by mixing an ethanolic solution (15 ml) of CdCl₂.2.5H₂O or Pb(NO₃)₂ (2.4 mmol) with 1,4-benzenedicarboxylate (0.4 g, 2.4 mmol in 15 ml 0.1 M NaOH). A solution of ABZ (0.362 g, 2.4 mmol) in 15 ml ethanol was then added to the mixture. The solution mixture was then refluxed and cooled to room temperature. The separated complexes were filtered, washed with distilled water and ethanol and dried in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Physical measurements :

The stoichiometric analyses (C, H, N, S) were performed using Analyischer Funktionstest Vario El Fab-Nr.1182027 elemental analyzer. The conductance was measured using conductivity meter model 4310 JENWAY. The IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer and the electronic spectra were obtained using a Shimadzu UV-2101 PC spectrophotometer. Thermal studies were carried out in dynamic air on a Shimadzu DTG 60-H thermal analyzer at a heating rate 10 °C min⁻¹.

Voltammetric studies :

Apparatus :

The cyclic voltammograms were obtained using an EG&G Princeton Applied Research Corporation (PAR) 264A polarographic analyzer/stripping voltammeter, coupled with PAR Model 303 A Static Mercury Drop Electrode (SMDE). The polarographic cell (PAR Model K0060) was fitted with Ag/AgCl saturated KCl and used as a reference electrode and a platinum wire as an auxiliary one.

Supporting electrolyte :

A stock solution (1 M) of tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP), *n*-Bu₄NClO₄ (Fluka) was used as a supporting electrolyte (0.1 M). A conventional sample cell operating under an atmosphere of prepurified nitrogen was used for cyclic voltammetry.

Experimental procedure for cyclic voltammetry :

1 ml of 1.0 M TBAP was transferred into the voltammetric cell (10 ml) (final concentration is 0.1 M at pH ~6.15) and the solution was deaerated by passing nitrogen for 16 min. The initial potential was controlled at +0.1 V and the scan rate used was 100 mV/s. The suitable amount of the complex stock solution (0.01 M) was introduced to give usually 10^{-4} M in the cell. The cyclic voltammograms were recorded and the final potential was attained at 1 V. All the experimental measurements were carried out at 25 ± 1 °C.

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